

GENERALIZED CONVEXITIES : HERMITE-HADAMARD INEQUALITIES AND THEIR QUANTUM ESTIMATES

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, some new convexities related to harmonic convexity have been defined and for each new convexity, a corresponding Hermite-Hadamard inequality has been proved. The product of functions having a particular convexity has been considered. The q -analogues of these inequalities have also been obtained.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Convexity is a very important notion which plays an important and sometimes essential role in several areas of mathematical sciences. It leads to many useful inequalities and among them one such inequality is referred to as the Hermite-Hadamard inequality discovered first by Hermite in 1881 : For a convex function $f : [\eta_1, \eta_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the following inequality persists:

$$f \frac{\eta_1 + \eta_2}{2} \leq \frac{1}{\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} f(x) dx \leq \frac{f(\eta_1) + f(\eta_2)}{2}.$$

Now-a-days several hundred papers exist dealing with Hermite-Hadamard inequalities.

In the process, several different type of convexities have been defined, to name a few, quasi-convexity, m -convexity, (α, m) -convexity, Arithmetic-Harmonic (AH)-convexity, m -AH-convexity, (α, m) -AH-convexity etc. In each case, Hermite-Hadamard inequality has been investigated in one and in some cases in higher dimensions as well. We refer to [2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16] and the references therein for further information on this subject.

Inspired by the work of Iscan [6, 7] who defined harmonic convexity, we generalize, in this paper, this convexity to m -harmonic convexity and further to (α, m) -harmonic convexity. Moreover, we also define new notions of harmonic-geometric (HG)-convexity, m - HG -convexity and (α, m) - HG -convexity. For each of these convexities, we prove Hermite-Hadamard inequalities. Also, we provide inequalities involving the product of each of the above type of convexities.

Our next considerations, in this paper, is the quantum calculus or more commonly known as q -calculus. Although, the notion of q -calculus is very old, developed by Euler in 1740s and used by Gauss in 1812, during the last two decades, people started reinvesting this topic and applied in almost all the branches of mathematical as well as other sciences. We mention to the books [1, 14] for various notations and theory of q -calculus.

In the field of inequalities, let us mention the papers [8, 16], where several known differences have been developed in the framework of q -calculus. Recently, in [1], the authors have studied q analogue of Hermite-Hadamard inequalities. In the present paper, we also derive the q -analogues of the Hermite-Hadamard inequalities for the new convexities that we derive here.

2. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

An interval is defined as $I = [\eta_1, \eta_2]$. Iscan [7] defined the notion of harmonically convex function as follows: A function f is said to be harmonically convex if $f : I \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for any $s \in [0, 1]$, if

$$f \left(\frac{xy}{sx + (1-s)y} \right) \leq sf(x) + (1-s)f(y), \quad x, y \in I.$$

The following Hermite-Hadamard inequality was proved in [7] for harmonically convex functions.

Theorem 2.1. *Let $f : I \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a harmonically convex function. The following inequalities are then true:*

$$f \left(\frac{2\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_1 + \eta_2} \right) \leq \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{f(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \frac{f(\eta_1) + f(\eta_2)}{2} \quad (2.1)$$

First we give some preliminaries of q -calculus.

The q -derivative of a continuous function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ at any point $x \in I$ is defined by

$${}_{\eta_1}D_q f(x) = \frac{f(x) - f(qx + (1-q)\eta_1)}{(1-q)(x - \eta_1)}, \quad x \neq \eta_1$$

and

$${}_{\eta_1}D_q f(\eta_1) = \lim_{x \rightarrow \eta_1} {}_{\eta_1}D_q f(x)$$

The q -integral of a continuous function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined by

$$\int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} f(s)_{\eta_1} d_q s = (1 - q)(x - \eta_1) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^n f(q^n x + (1 - q^n)\eta_1)$$

and for $c \in (\eta_1, x)$

$$\int_c^x f(s)_{\eta_1} d_q s = \int_{\eta_1}^x f(s)_{\eta_1} d_q s - \int_{\eta_1}^c f(s)_{\eta_1} d_q s.$$

The q -analogue of any real number $x \in \mathbb{R}$ is defined by

$$[x]_q := \frac{q^x - 1}{q - 1}.$$

For any integer $n \geq 1$, the q -analogue of $(x - c)^n$ is the polynomial

$$(x - c)_q^n := (x - c)(x - qc) \dots (x - q^{n-1}c).$$

To deal with the negative integer exponents, it is known that

$$(x - c)_q^{-n} = \frac{1}{(x - q^{-n}c)_q^n}.$$

The following derivatives are known for any integer $n \in \mathbb{Z}$

$$\begin{aligned} {}_{\eta_1} D_q (x - c)_q^n &= [n]_q (x - c)_q^{n-1}. \\ D_q \frac{1}{(x - c)_q^n} &= \frac{[-n]_q}{(x - q^n c)_q^{n-1}}. \end{aligned}$$

For more on the theory of q -calculus, we refer to the books [1, 14].

3. MAIN RESULTS

3.1 Harmonically Convex Function

We generalize harmonic convexity as follows:

Definition 3.1. A function $f : I \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be m -harmonically convex if for any $m, s \in [0, 1]$

$$f \left(\frac{mxy}{sx + m(1 - s)y} \right) \leq sf(x) + m(1 - s)f(y), \quad x, y \in I.$$

The notion of m -harmonic convexity can further be generalized as follows:

Definition 3.2. A function $f : I \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be (α, m) -harmonically convex if for any $m, t, \alpha \in [0, 1]$

$$f \frac{mxy}{sx + m(1 - s)y} \leq s^\alpha f(x) + m(1 - s^\alpha)f(y), \quad x, y \in I.$$

For (α, m) -harmonically convex functions, we prove the following:

Theorem 3.3. Let $f : I \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an (α, m) -harmonically convex function. Then the following inequalities hold:

$$(i) \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1} \int_{m\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{f(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \frac{f(\eta_2) + m\alpha f(\eta_1)}{\alpha + 1} \tag{3.1}$$

$$(ii) f \frac{2m\eta_1\eta_2}{m\eta_1 + \eta_2} \leq \frac{2m\eta_1\eta_2(1 - A)A^\alpha}{(\eta_2 - m\eta_1)} \int_{2m\eta_1(1-A)}^{2\eta_2(1-A)} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega + \frac{2m\eta_1\eta_2A(1 - A^\alpha)}{(\eta_2 - m\eta_1)} \int_{2\eta_1A}^{2\eta_2A/m} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega, \tag{3.2}$$

where $A = \frac{m}{1+m} \frac{1}{\alpha}$.

Proof. (i) From the definition of (α, m) -harmonic convexity, we have

$$f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1 - s)\eta_1} \leq s^\alpha f(\eta_2) + m(1 - s^\alpha)f(\eta_1) \tag{3.3}$$

which on integrating over $[0, 1]$ with respect to s gives

$$\int_0^1 f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1 - s)\eta_1} ds \leq f(\eta_2) \int_0^1 s^\alpha ds + mf(\eta_1) \int_0^1 (1 - s^\alpha) ds.$$

Now, by variable substitution $x = \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1}$ on the left side and solving the right side of the above inequality immediately gives (3.1).

(ii) Since (3.3) holds for all $s \in [0, 1]$, in particular, it holds for $s = \frac{m}{1+m} \frac{1}{\alpha} =: A$, i.e.,

$$f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{A\eta_2 + (1 - A)m\eta_1} \leq A^\alpha f(\eta_2) + m(1 - A^\alpha)f(\eta_1) \tag{3.4}$$

Take

$$\eta_1 = \frac{2xyA}{sy + mx(1 - s)}, \quad \eta_2 = \frac{2mxy(1 - A)}{mxs + (1 - s)y} \tag{3.5}$$

Then

$$\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{A\eta_2 + (1 - A)m\eta_1} = \frac{\frac{2mxyA}{sy + mx(1-s)} \cdot \frac{2mxy(1-A)}{mxs + (1-s)y}}{\frac{2mxy(1-A)}{mxs + (1-s)y} + \frac{2mxyA(1-A)}{sy + mx(1-s)}} = \frac{2mxy}{mx + y}$$

that is

$$f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{A\eta_2 + (1 - A)m\eta_1} = f \frac{2mxy}{mx + y}$$

which on integrating with respect to s on $[0, 1]$ gives

$$\int_0^1 f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{A\eta_2 + (1 - A)m\eta_1} ds = f \frac{2mxy}{mx + y} \tag{3.6}$$

Now, with η_1 and η_2 given by (3.5), the right side of (3.4) becomes

$$A^\alpha f \frac{2mxy(1 - A)}{mxs + (1 - s)y} + m(1 - A^\alpha) f \frac{2xyA}{sy + mx(1 - s)} \tag{3.7}$$

which on integrating with respect to s on $[0, 1]$ becomes

$$A^\alpha I_1 + m(1 - A^\alpha) I_2,$$

where

$$I_1 = \int_0^1 f \frac{2mxy(1 - A)}{mxs + (1 - s)y} ds$$

and

$$I_2 = \int_0^1 f \frac{2mxyA}{sy + mx(1 - s)} ds.$$

For solving I_1 , put $\frac{mxy(1-A)}{mxs+(1-s)y} = z$ so that $ds = \frac{mxy(1-A)}{(y-mx)z^2} dz$ and as $s \rightarrow 0, z \rightarrow mx(1 - A)$ and as $s \rightarrow 1, z \rightarrow y(1 - A)$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \frac{mxy(1 - A)}{y - mx} \int_{mx(1-A)}^{y(1-A)} \frac{f(2z)}{z^2} dz \\ &= \frac{2mxy(1 - A)}{y - mx} \int_{2mx(1-A)}^{2y(1-A)} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega. \end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

Similarly, by taking $\frac{xyA}{sy+mx(1-s)} = z$, it can be shown that

$$I_2 = \frac{2xyA}{y - mx} \int_{2xA}^{2yA/m} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega. \tag{3.9}$$

Thus, integrating (3.4) with respect to s over $[0, 1]$ and using (3.6) - (3.9), we obtain

$$f \frac{2mxy}{mx + y} \leq \frac{2mxy(1 - A)A^\alpha}{(y - mx)} \int_{2mx(1-A)}^{2y(1-A)} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega + \frac{2mxyA(1 - A^\alpha)}{y - mx} \int_{2xA}^{2yA/m} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega$$

and rewriting x and y as respectively η_1 and η_2 , we get

$$f \frac{2m\eta_1\eta_2}{m\eta_1 + \eta_2} \leq \frac{2m\eta_1\eta_2(1-A)A^\alpha}{(\eta_2 - m\eta_1)} \int_{2m\eta_1(1-A)}^{2\eta_2(1-A)} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega + \frac{2m\eta_1\eta_2A(1-A^\alpha)}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1} \int_{2\eta_1A}^{2\eta_2A/m} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega.$$

This completes the proof. □

Remark 3.4. If $\alpha = m = 1$, then $A = \frac{1}{2}$ and therefore, in this case, both the integrals on the right side of (3.2) becomes equal to $\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{2(\eta_2 - \eta_1)} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega$. Consequently, (3.2) and (3.3) together become (2.1).

Our next consideration is about the product of (α, m) -HA convex functions. We prove the following:

Theorem 3.5. *The product of two (α, m) -HA convex functions is also an (α, m) -HA convex function.*

Proof. By definition, for any $x, y \in I$ we have for two (α, m) -HA convex functions f and g , and for any $s \in [0, 1]$

$$f \frac{mxy}{sy + m(1-s)x} \leq s^\alpha f(y) + m(1-t^\alpha)f(x)$$

and

$$g \frac{mxy}{sy + m(1-s)x} \leq s^\alpha g(y) + m(1-s^\alpha)g(x)$$

which together give that

$$\begin{aligned} f \frac{mxy}{sy + m(1-s)x} g \frac{mxy}{sy + m(1-s)x} &\leq (s^\alpha f(y) + m(1-s^\alpha)f(x))(s^\alpha g(y) + m(1-s^\alpha)g(x)) \\ &\leq s^{2\alpha} f(y)g(y) + m^2(1-t^\alpha)^2 f(x)g(x). \\ &\leq s^\alpha f(y)g(y) + m(1-t^\alpha)f(x)g(x) \\ &= s^\alpha (fg)(y) + m(1-s^\alpha)(fg)(x). \end{aligned}$$

and the assertion follows. □

Remark 3.6. From Theorem 3.5, it follows that the product of two m -HA convex functions is again an m -HA convex function which implies that the product of two HA convex functions is again so.

We shall be using the following notations:

$$K_{\eta_1} := f(\eta_1)g(\eta_1), K_{\eta_2} := f(\eta_2)g(\eta_2), K_{\frac{\eta_1}{\eta_2}} := f(\eta_1)g(\eta_2) + f(\eta_2)g(\eta_1).$$

Below, we prove a Hermite-Hadamard type inequality for the product of (α, m) -HA convex functions.

Theorem 3.7. Let $f, g : I \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be two (α, m) -HA convex functions. Then the following inequality holds:

$$\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{m\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{m\eta_2} \frac{f(x)g(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \frac{K_{\eta_2}}{2\alpha + 1} + \frac{2\alpha^2 m^2 K_{\eta_1}}{(\alpha + 1)(2\alpha + 1)} + \frac{m\alpha K_{\eta_2}^{\eta_1}}{(\alpha + 1)(2\alpha + 1)}. \tag{3.10}$$

Proof. Since f, g are two (α, m) -HA convex functions, then by definition, we have

$$f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \leq s^\alpha f(\eta_2) + m(1-s^\alpha)f(\eta_1)$$

and

$$g \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \leq s^\alpha g(\eta_2) + m(1-s^\alpha)g(\eta_1).$$

Since $f, g \geq 0$, we have

$$f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} g \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \leq s^{2\alpha} f(\eta_2)g(\eta_2) + m^2(1-s^\alpha)^2 f(\eta_1)g(\eta_1) + ms^\alpha(1-s^\alpha)(f(\eta_1)g(\eta_2) + f(\eta_2)g(\eta_1))$$

which on integrating with respect to s over $[0, 1]$ gives

$$\int_0^1 f \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} g \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} ds \leq K_{\eta_2} \int_0^1 s^{2\alpha} ds + m^2 K_{\eta_1} \int_0^1 (1-s^\alpha)^2 ds + mK_{\eta_2}^{\eta_1} \int_0^1 s^\alpha(1-s^\alpha) ds.$$

The assertion now follows by making variable substitution $x = \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1}$. □

Next, we provide a variant of Theorem (3.7), where the left side of (3.10) is independent of m .

Theorem 3.8. Let $f, g : I \subset \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be two (α, m) -HA convex functions. Then the following inequality holds:

$$\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{f(x)g(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \frac{1}{2\alpha + 1} K_{\eta_2/m} + \frac{m^2\alpha^2 K_{\eta_1}}{\alpha + 1} + \frac{m\alpha K_{\eta_2/m}^{\eta_1}}{\alpha + 1}. \tag{3.11}$$

Proof. As f and g are (α, m) -HA convex functions, then by definition, we have

$$f \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2} = f \frac{m\eta_1 \frac{\eta_2}{m}}{s\eta_1 + m(1-s)\frac{\eta_2}{m}} \leq s^\alpha f \frac{\eta_2}{m} + m(1-s^\alpha)f(\eta_1)$$

and

$$g \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{t\eta_1 + (1-t)\eta_2} = g \frac{m\eta_1 \frac{\eta_2}{m}}{t\eta_1 + m(1-t)\frac{\eta_2}{m}} \leq t^\alpha g \frac{\eta_2}{m} + m(1-t^\alpha)g(\eta_1).$$

The assertion now follows in the same way as in Theorem 3.7. □

3.2 Harmonically Geometric Convex Function

Here, we define certain new type of convexities as follows.

Definition 3.9. A function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be

(i) harmonically-geometric (HG) convex or harmonically log convex if

$$f \frac{1}{\frac{s}{x} + \frac{1-s}{y}} \leq (f(y))^s (f(x))^{1-s}$$

(ii) m -harmonically-geometric (m -HG) convex or m -harmonically log convex if

$$f \frac{1}{\frac{s}{mx} + \frac{1-s}{y}} \leq (f(y))^s (f(x))^{m(1-s)}$$

(iii) (α, m) -harmonically-geometric $((\alpha, m)$ -HG) convex or (α, m) -harmonically log convex if

$$f \frac{1}{\frac{s}{mx} + \frac{1-s}{y}} \leq (f(y))^{s^\alpha} (f(x))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

holds for all $x, y \in I$ and $s \in [0, 1], m \in (0, 1], \alpha \in (0, 1]$.

We prove the following:

Theorem 3.10. Let f be an HG convex function. Then the following Hermite-Hadamard inequality holds:

$$\log \frac{2\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_1 + \eta_2} \leq \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \log \sqrt{f(\eta_1)f(\eta_2)}. \tag{3.12}$$

Proof. By the definition of HG convex function, we have

$$f \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + (1-s)\eta_1} \leq (f(\eta_2))^s (f(\eta_1))^{1-s}$$

Taking logarithm on both sides and integrating with respect to t over $[0, 1]$, we get

$$\int_0^1 \log f \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + (1-s)\eta_1} \leq \log f(\eta_2) \int_0^1 s ds + \log f(\eta_1) \int_0^1 (1-s) ds = \frac{\log f(\eta_1) + \log f(\eta_2)}{2}$$

or

$$\int_0^1 \log f \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + (1-s)\eta_1} \leq \log \sqrt{f(\eta_1)f(\eta_2)}.$$

By making the variable substitution $x = \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2+(1-s)\eta_1}$ in the last inequality, we get

$$\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \log \sqrt{f(\eta_1)f(\eta_2)}. \tag{3.13}$$

Next, taking $s = \frac{1}{2}$ in the definition of HG convex function gives

$$f \frac{2\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_1 + \eta_2} \leq \sqrt{f(\eta_1)f(\eta_2)}.$$

In the last inequality, take $\eta_1 = \frac{xy}{sx+(1-s)y}$, $\eta_2 = \frac{xy}{sy+(1-s)x}$ so that we obtain

$$f \frac{\frac{2xy}{\frac{sx+(1-s)y}{xy} + \frac{xy}{sy+(1-s)x}}}{sx+(1-s)y} \leq f \frac{xy}{sx+(1-s)y} f \frac{xy}{sy+(1-s)x}$$

or

$$f \frac{2xy}{x+y} \leq f \frac{xy}{sx+(1-s)y} f \frac{xy}{sy+(1-s)x}$$

which on taking logarithm on both sides gives

$$\log f \frac{2xy}{x+y} \leq \frac{1}{2} \log f \frac{xy}{sx+(1-s)y} + \log f \frac{xy}{sy+(1-s)x}$$

Integrating with respect to s over $[0, 1]$, we get

$$\log \int_0^1 f \frac{2xy}{x+y} ds \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_0^1 \log f \frac{xy}{sx+(1-s)y} ds + \int_0^1 \log f \frac{xy}{sy+(1-s)x} ds .$$

Since each integral on right side equals to $\int_{y=x}^{xy} \frac{\log f(u)}{u^2} du$, we have

$$\log f \frac{2xy}{x+y} \leq \frac{1}{2} \frac{2xy}{x+y} \int_x^y \frac{\log f(u)}{u^2} du = \frac{xy}{y-x} \int_x^y \frac{\log f(u)}{u^2} du$$

Replacing x and y by η_1 and η_2 , respectively, we have

$$\log f \frac{2\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_1 + \eta_2} \leq \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x)}{x^2} dx. \tag{3.14}$$

On combining the inequalities (3.13) and (3.14), we get (3.12) and the proof is complete. \square

The next result is regarding (α, m) -HG convex functions.

Theorem 3.11. Let $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be an (α, m) -HG convex function. Then the following inequalities hold:

$$(i) \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1} \int_{m\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \frac{1}{\alpha + 1} [\log f(\eta_2) + m\alpha \log f(\eta_1)] \tag{3.15}$$

$$(ii) \log f \frac{2mxy}{mx+y} \leq \frac{2mxy(1-A)A^\alpha}{(y-mx)} \int_{2mx(1-A)}^{2y(1-A)} \frac{\log f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega + \frac{2mxyA(1-A^\alpha)}{y-mx} \int_{2xA}^{2yA/m} \frac{\log f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega \tag{3.16}$$

Proof. (i) In view of the definitions of (α, m) -HG convex functions, for any $\eta_1, \eta_2 \in I$, we have

$$f\left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1}\right) \leq (f(\eta_2))^{s^\alpha} (f(\eta_1))^{m(1-s^\alpha)} \tag{3.17}$$

which on taking log on both sides and integrating with respect to s over $[0, 1]$ gives

$$\int_0^1 \log f\left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1}\right) ds \leq \log f(\eta_2) \int_0^1 s^\alpha ds + m \log f(\eta_1) \int_0^1 (1-s^\alpha) ds$$

The inequality (3.15) now follows by making variable substitution $x = \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1}$ and solving the integrals on the right side.

(ii) We proceed as in Theorem 3.3 (ii). We apply (3.17) for $s = A$ and get

$$f\left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{A\eta_2 + m(1-A)\eta_1}\right) \leq (f(\eta_2))^{A^\alpha} (f(\eta_1))^{m(1-A^\alpha)}. \tag{3.18}$$

Again, on taking η_1 and η_2 as in (3.5), the left side of (3.17) after taking log and integrating with respect to s over $[0, 1]$ becomes

$$\log f\left(\frac{2mxy}{mx + y}\right) \tag{3.19}$$

while the right side becomes

$$A^\alpha \int_0^1 \log f\left(\frac{2mxy(1-A)}{mxs + (1-s)y}\right) ds + m(1-A^\alpha) \int_0^1 \log f\left(\frac{2mxyA}{sy + mx(1-s)}\right) ds \tag{3.20}$$

The integrals in (3.20) can be simplified as done for calculating I_1 and I_2 in Theorem 3.3(ii) combining which and (3.19), we get

$$\log f\left(\frac{2mxy}{mx + y}\right) \leq \frac{2mxy(1-A)A^\alpha}{(y-mx)} \int_{2mx(1-A)}^{2y(1-A)} \frac{\log f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega + \frac{2mxyA(1-A^\alpha)}{y-mx} \int_{2xA}^{2yA/m} \frac{\log f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega.$$

Now, rewriting x, y as respectively, a, b gives (3.16). □

Remark 3.12. Similar to Remark 3.4, if $\alpha = m = 1$, then $A = \frac{1}{2}$ and therefore both integrals on the right side of (3.16) become equal to

$$\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{2(\eta_2 - \eta_1)} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(\omega)}{\omega^2} d\omega$$

Consequently, in this case both (3.15) and (3.16) combined together give (2.1).

Our next consideration is about the product of (α, m) -HG convex functions. As in Theorem 3.5, it can be proved that the products of two (α, m) -HG convex functions is again (α, m) -HG convex function.

Now, we prove the following:

Theorem 3.13. Let $f, g : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be (α, m) -HG convex functions. The following inequality thus persists:

$$\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1} \int_{m\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x) + \log g(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \frac{\log K_{\eta_2} + m\alpha \log K_{\eta_1}}{\alpha + 1} \tag{3.21}$$

Proof. This can be obtained similar to Theorem 3.7 by using the definitions of (α, m) -HG convex functions. □

Below, we provide a variant of Theorem 3.13 in which the left side of (3.21) is independent of m .

Theorem 3.14. Let $f, g : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be (α, m) -HG convex functions. The following inequality is then true:

$$\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - \eta_1} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x) + \log g(x)}{x^2} dx \leq \frac{\log K_{\eta_2/m} + m\alpha \log K_{\eta_1}}{\alpha + 1} \tag{3.22}$$

Proof. As f and g are (α, m) -HG convex functions, then by definition, we have

$$f \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2} = f \frac{m\eta_1 \frac{\eta_2^2}{m}}{s\eta_1 + m(1-s)\frac{\eta_2^2}{m}} \leq f \frac{\eta_2}{m} {}^{s\alpha} (f(\eta_1))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

and

$$g \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2} = g \frac{m\eta_1 \frac{\eta_2^2}{m}}{s\eta_1 + m(1-s)\frac{\eta_2^2}{m}} \leq g \frac{\eta_2}{m} {}^{s\alpha} (g(\eta_1))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

On multiplying the above inequalities and taking \log on both sides, we have

$$\log f \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2} + \log g \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2} \leq s^\alpha \log K_{\eta_2/m} + m(1-s^\alpha) \log K_{\eta_1}$$

which on integrating with respect to s over $[0, 1]$ and making variable substitution $x = \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2}$ on left sides, we obtain (3.22). □

3.3 The Framework of q -Calculus

This subsection is devoted to the inequalities proved in the previous subsections for q -calculus. We prove the following theorem which provides a q -analogue of Hermite-Hadamard inequality for product of (α, m) -HA convex functions.

Theorem 3.15. Let $f, g : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be two (α, m) -HA convex functions. The following inequalities are then true:

$$\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{q(\eta_2 - m\eta_1)} \int_{m\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{f(x)g(x)}{x^2} {}_{\eta_1}d_q x \leq \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} K_{\eta_2} + m^2 K_{\eta_1} \left(1 - \frac{2}{[\alpha + 1]_q} + \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} \right) + mK_{\eta_2}^{\eta_1} \left(\frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} - \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} \right) \tag{3.23}$$

Proof. By the definition of (α, m) -HA convex functions applied on f and g , we get

$$f \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) \leq s^\alpha f(\eta_2) + m(1-s^\alpha)f(\eta_1)$$

and

$$g \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) \leq s^\alpha g(\eta_2) + m(1-s^\alpha)g(\eta_1).$$

Since $f, g \geq 0$, multiplying the above inequalities and taking q -integral from 0 to 1 on both sides, we obtain

$$\int_0^1 f \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) g \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) {}_0d_q s \leq K_{\eta_2} \int_0^1 s^{2\alpha} {}_0d_q s + m^2 K_{\eta_1} \int_0^1 (1-s^\alpha)^2 {}_0d_q s + mK_{\eta_2}^{\eta_1} \int_0^1 s^\alpha(1-s^\alpha) {}_0d_q s \tag{3.24}$$

Note that

$$\int_0^1 s^{2\alpha} {}_0d_q s = (1-q) \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} q^{n(2\alpha+1)} = (1-q) \cdot \frac{1}{1-q^{2\alpha+1}} = \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q}$$

Similarly, it can be calculated that

$$\int_0^1 (1-s^\alpha)^2 {}_0d_q s = 1 - \frac{2}{[\alpha + 1]_q} + \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q}$$

and

$$\int_0^1 s^\alpha(1-s^\alpha) {}_0d_q s = \frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} - \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q}$$

Further, if we take

$$x = \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1},$$

$$s = \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1} \cdot \frac{1}{x} - \frac{m\eta_1}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1}$$

and it can be concluded that

$${}_0 D_{q,s} = \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1} [-1]_q(x)_{q^{-2}} = \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{\eta_2 - m\eta_1} \frac{1}{q} \frac{1}{x^2} .$$

Moreover, when $s \rightarrow 0, x \rightarrow \eta_2$ and when $s \rightarrow 1, x \rightarrow \eta_1$. Thus by applying the above considerations, the inequality (3.24) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{q(\eta_2 - m\eta_1)} \int_{m\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{f(x)g(x)}{x^2} {}_{\eta_1} d_q x &\leq \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} K_{\eta_2} + m^2 K_{\eta_1} \left(1 - \frac{2}{[\alpha + 1]_q} + \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} \right) \\ &\quad + mK_{\eta_2}^{\eta_1} \left(\frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} - \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and the theorem is proved. □

Remark 3.16. For $\alpha = 1$, Theorem 3.3 gives the m -HA Hermite-Hadamard inequalities for product of functions. Further if $m = 1$ as well, then the corresponding inequality is obtained for HA-convex functions. Next, we prove a variant of Theorem 3.15 where the left side of (3.23) is independent of m .

Theorem 3.17. Let $f, g : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be two (α, m) -HA convex functions. Then the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{q(\eta_2 - \eta_1)} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{f(x)g(x)}{x^2} {}_{\eta_1} d_q x &\leq \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} K_{\eta_2/m} + m^2 K_{\eta_1} \left(1 - \frac{2}{[\alpha + 1]_q} + \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} \right) \\ &\quad + mK_{\eta_2/m}^{\eta_1} \left(\frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} - \frac{1}{[2\alpha + 1]_q} \right) . \end{aligned}$$

Proof. As f and g are (α, m) -HA convex functions, then by definition, we have

$$f \left(\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2} \right) = f \left(\frac{m\eta_1 \frac{\eta_2^2}{m}}{s\eta_1 + m(1-s)\frac{\eta_2^2}{m}} \right) \leq s^\alpha f \left(\frac{\eta_2}{m} \right) + m(1-s^\alpha) f(\eta_1)$$

and

$$g \left(\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_1 + (1-s)\eta_2} \right) = g \left(\frac{m\eta_1 \frac{\eta_2^2}{m}}{s\eta_1 + m(1-s)\frac{\eta_2^2}{m}} \right) \leq s^\alpha g \left(\frac{\eta_2}{m} \right) + m(1-s^\alpha) g(\eta_1)$$

. The assertion now follows proceeding in the same as in Theorem 3.15. □

The next theorem is the q -analogue of Theorem 3.13.

Theorem 3.18. Let $f, g : I \subset \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be two (α, m) -HG convex functions. Then the following inequality persists:

$$\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{q(\eta_2 - m\eta_1)} \int_{m\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x) + \log g(x)}{x^2} {}_{m\eta_1} d_q x \leq \frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} \log K_{\eta_1} + m \left(1 - \frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} \right) \log K_{\eta_2} . \tag{3.25}$$

Proof. By definition, we have

$$f \left(\frac{1}{\frac{s}{m\eta_1} + \frac{1-s}{\eta_2}} \right) \leq (f(\eta_2))^{s^\alpha} (f(\eta_1))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

and

$$g \left(\frac{1}{\frac{s}{m\eta_1} + \frac{1-s}{\eta_2}} \right) \leq (g(\eta_2))^{s^\alpha} (g(\eta_1))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

which give that

$$f \left(\frac{1}{\frac{s}{m\eta_1} + \frac{1-s}{\eta_2}} \right) g \left(\frac{1}{\frac{s}{m\eta_1} + \frac{1-s}{\eta_2}} \right) \leq (f(\eta_1)g(\eta_1))^{s^\alpha} (f(\eta_2)g(\eta_2))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

or

$$\log f \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) + \log g \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) \leq s^\alpha \log K_{\eta_1} + m(1-s^\alpha) \log K_{\eta_2}$$

Taking q -integral with respect to s over $[0, 1]$, we obtain

$$\int_0^1 \log f \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) d_q s + \int_0^1 \log g \left(\frac{m\eta_1\eta_2}{s\eta_2 + m(1-s)\eta_1} \right) d_q s \leq \log K_{\eta_1} \int_0^1 s^\alpha d_q t + m \log K_{\eta_2} \int_0^1 (1-s^\alpha) d_q s$$

The assertion now follows proceeding in the similar way as in Theorem 3.15. □

Next, we give a variant of Theorem 3.18 so as to make the left side of (3.25) is independent of m .

Theorem 3.19. *Let $f, g : I \subset \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be two (α, m) -HG convex functions. Then the following inequality holds:*

$$\frac{\eta_1\eta_2}{q(\eta_2 - \eta_1)} \int_{\eta_1}^{\eta_2} \frac{\log f(x) + \log g(x)}{x^2} d_q x \leq \frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} \log K_{\eta_1/m} + m \left(1 - \frac{1}{[\alpha + 1]_q} \right) \log K_{\eta_2} \tag{3.26}$$

Proof. Since f and g are (α, m) -HG convex, we have

$$f \left(\frac{1}{\frac{s}{\eta_1} + \frac{1-s}{\eta_2}} \right) = f \left(\frac{1}{\frac{s}{\frac{m\eta_1}{m}} + \frac{1-s}{\eta_2}} \right) \leq f \left(\frac{\eta_1}{m} \right)^{s^\alpha} (f(\eta_2))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

and similarly,

$$g \left(\frac{1}{\frac{s}{\eta_1} + \frac{1-s}{\eta_2}} \right) \leq g \left(\frac{\eta_1}{m} \right)^{s^\alpha} (g(\eta_2))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}$$

which give that

$$f \frac{\eta_1 \eta_2}{s\eta_2 + (1-s)\eta_1} g \frac{\eta_1 \eta_2}{s\eta_2 + (1-s)\eta_1} \leq f \frac{\eta_1}{m} g \frac{\eta_1}{m} s^\alpha (f(\eta_2)g(\eta_2))^{m(1-s^\alpha)}.$$

or

$$\log f \frac{\eta_1 \eta_2}{s\eta_2 + (1-s)\eta_1} + \log g \frac{\eta_1 \eta_2}{s\eta_2 + (1-s)\eta_1} \leq s^\alpha \log f \frac{\eta_1}{m} g \frac{\eta_1}{m} + m(1-s^\alpha) \log(f(\eta_2)g(\eta_2)).$$

Taking q -integral with respect to s over $[0, 1]$ and proceeding as in Theorem 3.15, the assertion follows. \square

4. Conclusion

We conclude that in this paper some new convexities related to harmonic convexity have been defined and a corresponding Hermite-Hadamard inequalities have been established. It has also been presented the product of functions of particular convexities and their q -analogues.

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